

FRONTIERS

science journalism initiative

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

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Project information

Project name	FRONTIERS
Full project name	Fellowship Residencies Offering Science News professionals Tools and training for Independent and Ethical Reporting on Science
Grant number	101121863
Project coordinator	Mr. Yoram Bar-Zeev, Enspire Science Ltd. ybz@enspire-science.com
Project duration	01/06/2023-31/05/2027

Document information

Deliverable name and number	D5.2 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan		
Due date	30/11/2023		
Actual submission date	10/12/2023		
Contributing partners	NOVA University of Lisbon, Center for Ethics in Science and Science Journalism (CESJ), Universidad Pompeu Fabra, Enspire Science.		
Deliverable type	R	Document, report	X
	DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
	DEC	Websites, patent filings, videos etc.	
	DMP	Data Management Plan	
Dissemination Level	PU	Public	X
	SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

Version history

Version	Date	Authors	Organization	Comments
1.0	21/11/2023	A. Sanchez, A. Granado, R. Silva	NOVA University of Lisbon	First draft
Final	10/12/2023	A. Sanchez, A. Granado, R. Silva	NOVA University of Lisbon	Final Version

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Funded by the European Union (EU) through the European Research Council (ERC) grant FRONTIERS, nr 101121863. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the EU or the ERC Executive Agency. Neither the EU nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The subgrants are not given by the EU or the ERC.

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

FRONTIERS	Fellowship Residencies Offering science News professionals Tools and training for Independent and Ethical Reporting on Science
CSO	Coordination and Support Office
ERC	European Research Council
EU	European Union
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
WP	Work Packages

FRONTIERS Glossary

Applicant Journalists	Science journalists who have applied or will apply for FRONTIERS science journalist residencies.
FRONTIERS Fellows	Science journalists who have been selected for one of the FRONTIERS science journalism residencies.

FRONTIERS Alumni	Science journalists who have taken part in past FRONTIERS Residencies.
Journalistic Outputs	Materials produced by the science journalists during the residencies (e.g. articles, books, videos, podcasts, etc.).
Host Institution	Research centre/institute welcoming a FRONTIERS Fellow
Host Researcher(s)	Researcher(s) at Host Institution, who are the scientific mentors of FRONTIERS Fellows
Potential Host Institution	Research centre/institute that has expressed interest in supporting applicant journalists

1. Executive Summary

The overall objective of the present document, D5.2 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan, is to describe the communication strategy of the FRONTIERS project and to ensure that all communication and dissemination activities are coordinated. Additionally, D5.2 highlights plans for the further exploitation of the project's activities and results, ensuring the best use and reproduction of science residency programs outside the scope of FRONTIERS.

The document begins with a general overview of the FRONTIERS project, a description of the WP5 "Dissemination and Communication", and an introduction to the FRONTIERS' branding and identity. In the next sections, the main target audiences are outlined, as well as the key messages and communication channels of the project. A plan for monitoring the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities is described in Chapter 7.

This deliverable is largely based on the Project Proposal and Grant Agreement and was improved with ongoing input from the Consortium's partners. This is a living document, subject to revisions and adaptations throughout the course of the project. A final version of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan, D5.5, will be delivered at the end of the project and will include such revisions.

2. Project Introduction

FRONTIERS aims to tackle the challenges of science journalism, specifically in the area of Frontier Science. The overall objective of the project is to establish a program supporting science journalists' residencies in research institutions located in an EU Member State or a country associated with the EU's Horizon Europe Programme.

Three core principles have been fundamental in the conception of this project and will guide the design and implementation of the residency's programs: i) ethical science reporting, ii) journalistic independence, and iii) coverage of Frontier Research. Ultimately, the project expects to strengthen the trust among science journalists, researchers and research institutions and promote better communication of Frontier Research to society.

Principles

The FRONTIERS project was created with the goal of contributing to tackling some of the challenges of **science journalism**, such as those related to the communication of the probabilistic nature of scientific results and the related uncertainty, and misinformation and disinformation spread in the digital and fast-paced media environment, the pressure on journalists to meet tight deadlines, the deteriorating employment conditions and resources available for science journalists, the need for greater diversity in areas covered by science journalists, the lack of structured and affordable programs for lifelong learning for science

journalists, as well as the lack of structured relationships and communication between scientists and science journalists.

Addressing such issues is only possible if **journalistic independence** is guaranteed. By establishing science journalism residencies, and providing financial support to the fellows, the FRONTIERS project will favour a bottom-up approach, allowing journalists to apply to any residency they desire, in any research institution located in an EU Member State, or a country associated with the EU's Horizon Europe Programme, of their choice.

Equally important in the context of this project is to ensure the coverage of **Frontier Research**. Calls for residencies will focus on innovative frontier research, hardly disseminated among the lay public, which poses specific challenges to journalists.

Objectives

Specific and measurable objectives have been set up at the start of the project:

1. Develop and implement an independent, credible, and ethical residency program to allow science journalists integration and immersion in Host Institutions.
2. Establish a Coordination and Support Office (CSO) to manage the ongoing work linked to the program.
3. Develop and deliver training content for science journalists, researchers, and research institutions to provide tools for effective science journalism of frontier research.
4. Establish bridges for interaction and cooperation between scientists and science journalists through networking and mutual events.
5. Explore the path towards sustainability of the program through local, national or EU-level funding opportunities

3. WP 5: Dissemination and Communication

In order to achieve the project's vision and objectives, a preliminary communication and dissemination strategy has been devised. The development of this strategy is inserted into the activities of Work Package 5 (WP5) (See Annex II for a detailed timeline of the WP5 tasks and deliverables).

WP5 aims to ensure that all relevant stakeholders are made aware of the project and its objectives, and it focuses on three main goals:

1. Engage journalists, researchers and research institutions in the FRONTIERS residencies, and highlight the benefits of the cross-talk (and cross-learning) between scientists and the media.
2. Raise awareness about the project for the scientific community, the media, and a cross-section of the general public, highlighting the importance of both frontier research and independent science journalism for an engaged democratic society.
3. Make sure the project has tangible outputs that contribute to inspiring funders, scientific institutions and journalists to replicate this experience in other contexts.

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

The development of a Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan is a fundamental step in achieving the goals proposed in WP5. This deliverable (D5.2 - Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan) was released at M6 of the project and covers the initial detailed description of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy of FRONTIERS.

According to the European Commission, a distinction should be made between these three concepts:

- **Dissemination** refers to the “public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means, including by scientific publications in any medium”. It ensures that the projects' results are made available to others.
- **Communication** refers to the “process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results”. Its focus is to inform about and promote the project and its results.
- **Exploitation** is the “utilization of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned”. The exploitation strategy focuses on making concrete use of research results.

The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan of FRONTIERS i) describes the project's brand and identity, ii) identifies its main target audiences, iii) establishes the appropriate communication channels and messages for each target audience and iv) serves as a guide for the partners of the consortium to execute project-related communication activities.

NOVA University Lisbon is the partner responsible for drafting and implementing this deliverable, while the remaining partners are also actively involved in the consolidation and execution of the communication activities hereby described.

The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan sets out a series of activities to achieve the following objectives:

- To inform and raise awareness about the project.
- To engage the stakeholders with the project's communication activities.
- To ensure that guidelines are set in place for a clear, uniform, and timely communication of the project.
- To disseminate the project's outputs.

This deliverable covers the entire course of the project's duration and will be updated at M48 (D5.5 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan – Final version), to include an analysis of the activities performed during the project and revisions to this document. In addition, the final version of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan will include a detailed impact analysis, focusing on measuring the impact of the project and ensuring an appropriate communication strategy for the long-term viability of the science journalism residencies. A more comprehensive Exploitation plan will also be present in D5.5, including a list of materials produced by the project's partners, with guidelines to ensure the replication of science residency programs outside the scope of FRONTIERS.

4. Branding and Identity

A clearly defined and easily recognisable branding and (visual) identity of a project is essential to achieve its best communication results.

Logo and Symbol

During the first months of the project, a logo was drafted and approved by the consortium (Figure 1). The logo is comprised of the project's acronym 'FRONTIERS'; the tag "science journalism initiative" lies below the acronym, and, on one hand, it summarizes the project, and, on the other hand, it represents its uniqueness and novelty.

The logo reflects the project's affiliation with the ERC through two key elements: Firstly, the use of orange, which is one of the project's primary colours, aligns with the colour scheme of the ERC logo. Additionally, the rounded design elements within the letter "O" of the FRONTIERS' logo mirror the elements found in the ERC logo. Taken together, these color choices and elements within FRONTIERS' logo, and its broader visual identity, evoke a connection to the ERC, its funding body.

Positive and negative versions of the logo have been created to ensure optimal visibility and readability across various backgrounds and mediums.

Additionally, a project symbol was created (in positive and negative versions), to help convey the project's visual identity in a simple, yet recognizable, manner (Figure 2). The project's logos and symbols are publicly available on the website.

Figure 1 - FRONTIERS logo (Positive)

Figure 2 - FRONTIERS symbol (Positive)

Templates

In line with the project's visual identity, a set of templates for reports (Figure 3) and presentations (Figure 4) was designed at the start of the project. These templates set the guidelines for colours and typography that unify and standardize the communication strategy of the project. Templates are designed to accommodate

different needs, including different page formats, and will be updated whenever necessary.

The templates are shared among all project partners via the Drive. Besides being a space for sharing and storing documents and feedback, the project's Drive is the preferred tool for general project management, while email is the main tool for messaging among the partners.

Figure 3 -Cover pages of the project's templates for reports.

Figure 4 - Cover slides of the project's templates for presentations.

Acknowledgement of EU Funding

According to Article 38 of the Grant Agreement, the beneficiaries of Horizon Europe, or past EU-funding actions, must acknowledge and ensure the visibility of EU funding in any communication material or activity related to the project.

FRONTIERS will acknowledge the ERC funding using the European Union emblem and ERC logo (figure 5) followed by the ERC funding statement “*Funded by the European Union (ERC, acronym, project number). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.*”

Figure 5 - European Union emblem and ERC logo for projects funded under Horizon Europe

5. Phases, target audiences, and key messages

Before setting out the main communication activities and channels, it is useful to understand how the FRONTIERS project was designed, to whom it is directed, and which key messages it aims to transmit to these audiences.

Phases

In order to achieve the project's objectives, the communication will be divided into three main phases:

- **Phase 1**

Objective: Attracting science journalists and scientific institutions to apply to FRONTIERS residencies.

- **Phase 2**

Objective: Sharing with a wider audience the experiences of journalists and institutions during the residencies.

- **Phase 3**

Objective: Ensuring the results and good practices of FRONTIERS are shared with potential funders, who could replicate the experience in other contexts.

There will be an overlap between the phases, as one residency ends and the following begins. Therefore, these phases will happen in a continuum throughout the entire duration of the project. This division is nevertheless useful since these distinct phases entail specific objectives and messages, delivered through different communication channels and to different target audiences (see Annex I).

Target audiences

Identifying the target audiences at the beginning of a project is crucial to establishing effective messages.

FRONTIERS' target audiences entail the main stakeholders of the project, which include **science journalists**, press officers and research managers at **research institutions**, and **researchers** working in these institutions. These audiences will be referred to as **primary target audiences**, and they are not only the main stakeholders of the communication strategy but also important actors and collaborators in the communication activities of the project.

In addition, the project communication and dissemination will cover **secondary target audiences**, which include:

- (Science) Journalist's associations
- Policymakers
- Horizon Europe National Contact Points (NCPs)
- National science funders

- Other potential funders
- Media organizations
- Scientific community in general
- General public.

Key messages

Establishing key messages is of crucial importance in the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan of FRONTIERS, as they will guide a clear and cohesive strategy, help deliver consistency and drive engagement with target audiences.

The FRONTIERS communication strategy has three main key messages:

1. Independent science journalism is an essential element for the proper functioning of democratic societies.
2. Frontier research is necessary for society, even if with no visible short-term application.
3. Bringing selected science journalists to interact closely with researchers and research institutions - while maintaining their full independence - will contribute to increasing trust in science and diminish irresponsible coverage of science issues.

These key messages are broken down into more specific messages and calls to action for each phase and target audience. Some examples are listed below:

Phase 1

- **Target Audiences:** Research institutions/researchers
Key Message: Promote independent and accurate science journalism by welcoming science journalists to work alongside researchers.
- **Target Audiences:** Journalists
Key Message: Develop your skills as a science journalist by experiencing frontier science first-hand, in total independence.

Phase 2

- **Target audiences:** Scientific community and Science Journalism community
Key Message: Learn about collaborations between journalists and researchers through the example of this FRONTIERS fellow's experience.
- **Target audiences:** Cross-section of the general public

Key Message: Independent science journalism plays an important role in bringing frontier science closer to society. Meet this FRONTIERS fellow.

Key Message: There are many places in Europe where frontier science is developed. Meet this FRONTIERS host institution.

Phase 3

- **Target audiences:** Policy makers / Funders

Key Message: Having journalists working side by side with scientists has many benefits. See them here.

Key Message: Consider implementing your own residency program. Let us show you how.

6. Communication Channels

Website

At the start of the project, a new website was set up at <https://www.frontiers.media> (Figure 6). The website is one of the main channels used in the communication of the project to the primary target audiences — science journalists, research institutions and researchers. It has been designed to serve as the main hub of information for the project, as well as a contact point between fellows and the CSO.

The website is not a mere repository of information, but also a central interface to promote dialogue, receive enquiries and reach a wider audience of individuals and groups that have a general interest in science journalism.

Figure 6 - Screenshot of the FRONTIERS' website homepage

In particular, the FRONTIERS website will serve as a communication channel to:

- **Announce open calls for upcoming science journalism residencies.**

One of the main purposes of the website is to announce open calls for upcoming science journalism residencies. A dedicated section on the website will provide detailed information, application FAQs, and deadlines, and serve as an entry point for journalists to apply for these residencies.

- **Disseminate the project's outputs.**

The FRONTIERS website will disseminate and highlight the outputs generated by the project, such as deliverables, handbooks, and journalistic work produced by past fellows during their residencies.

- **Promote the FRONTIERS' database of host institutions and researchers.**

At the beginning of the project, the CSO will collect expressions of interest from researchers and research institutions in Europe. The collection and assembling

of these expressions of interest will be used to mount a database with relevant information for potential applicants.

- **Share the experiences of FRONTIERS Alumni.**

Testimonials from past science journalism fellows will be featured on the FRONTIERS website. The first-hand accounts of experiences gained during past residencies may help to answer questions, motivate future applicants, and showcase the importance of Frontier Science.

- **Promote FRONTIERS events.**

Beyond residencies, the website will be used as a platform to promote FRONTIERS events, including the final conference, training sessions, workshops, and other project-related activities.

The structure and content of the website will be continuously updated by NOVA University Lisbon throughout the project, according to the inputs and needs of the target audiences and the project's partners.

Google Analytics is the tool used to monitor and measure the FRONTIERS' website traffic.

Social media

Social media channels will be used by FRONTIERS as tools for i) informing and promoting the project, ii) establishing a dialogue with stakeholders, iii) engaging potential interested audiences, and iv) sharing testimonials of past fellows.

The FRONTIERS social media approach will encompass the following objectives:

- **Promote the project.**

To ensure widespread awareness of the project, FRONTIERS' social media strategy will highlight the project's mission, objectives, and achievements.

Regular updates, including key milestones, events, and success stories from the journalist residencies, will be shared to cultivate interest from both the scientific and journalistic communities.

- **Expand the network of science journalists and host institutions.**

A targeted social media strategy will help FRONTIERS to broaden its network of science journalists and host institutions. Engaging with relevant communities on social media, including journalism associations, scientific organizations, and media professionals, will facilitate rapid and significant connections with stakeholders.

- **Establish a dialogue channel between stakeholders and the CSO.**

Social media platforms will facilitate a direct interaction between stakeholders and the CSO, enabling a dynamic and up-to-date exchange of information regarding the application process and ensuring a prompt response to questions by interested applicants.

In addition, after the completion of the fellowships, social media channels will be used to foster connections within the network of science journalists and share experiences from science journalist fellows.

- **Disseminate the project's results.**

Upon completion of residencies, the project's outputs will be shared across social media channels. FRONTIERS' strategy will favour a storytelling format to spotlight the journalistic outputs of past fellows.

The projects' deliverables will, when deemed relevant, be shared on social media platforms.

The FRONTIERS project is present on Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram and Youtube. (Table I). Twitter, Instagram and LinkedIn are the main social media channels since these are the platforms in which the majority of the stakeholders of the project are present, allowing the CSO to reach these target groups in a faster and more efficient manner. The YouTube channel will be primarily used as a tool for depositing, sharing and archiving the short videos produced by the FRONTIERS fellows and the final documentary. Videos deposited on the YouTube channel will be displayed on the project's website and newsletter via an embedded player and shared on the project's and partners' social media accounts.

Table I - FRONTIERS Social Media Handles and Links

Social Media Channel	Username	Link
Twitter	frontiers_media	https://twitter.com/frontiers_media
LinkedIn	frontiersmedia	https://www.linkedin.com/company/frontiersmedia/
Instagram	frontiers_media	https://www.instagram.com/frontiers_media/
YouTube	frontiers_media	www.youtube.com/@FRONTIERS_media

Communication via FRONTIERS' social media platforms will be implemented according to the following strategy:

- **Tailored messages for each channel.**

Communication through social media will align with the project's visual identity, ensuring consistency across platforms. At the same, content will be customized to best suit each platform's audience. Tailored hashtags will be used to enhance visibility and engagement.

- **Planning Social media content.**

A social media content planner will be created and discussed with all partners. This will ensure a collaborative and coordinated approach to the communication activities and strategy on social media channels.

- **Leveraging partners' institutional accounts.**

Besides the social media networks of the project, the communication of activities and dissemination of results will be amplified by the partners' institutional accounts.

- **Monitoring of content.**

FRONTIERS' social media channels will be closely monitored. This will allow partners to quickly respond to feedback, adapt messages, and foster connections with the audience.

A social media analytics report, with detailed data for each platform, will be regularly updated and shared in the consortium's Drive.

- **Takeover of social media channels by journalists.**

FRONTIERS will grant its fellows access to the project's social media accounts. This will allow them to share their residency experiences and final outputs; at the same time, a social media takeover by past fellows will foster proximity with stakeholders, especially with science journalists who may be interested in applying for future residencies.

Newsletter

The FRONTIERS newsletter can be an effective tool to ensure that stakeholders are informed about and engaged with the project. FRONTIERS newsletters will serve as a concise source of information and updates for a diverse audience, including journalists, research institutions, researchers, and science communication enthusiasts.

The project's newsletters will be brief and concise and will be used to:

- **Inform about the project.**

The FRONTIERS newsletter will deliver brief, but comprehensive, updates on the project's progress, objectives, and overall developments.

- **Announce open calls.**

Information regarding open calls for science journalism residencies, application deadlines, and guidelines will be communicated through the newsletters.

- **Promote upcoming events.**

The FRONTIERS newsletter will promote forthcoming events, including training sessions and the final conference organized by the project, and other relevant events in which the FRONTIERS partners are involved.

- **Disseminate the project's outputs.**

The FRONTIERS newsletter will be used to share the project's outputs such as deliverables, handbooks, and journalistic pieces generated through the project. This will allow the newsletter's subscribers to view and engage with the content produced by FRONTIERS' CSO and past fellows.

- **Inform about the project's achievements.**

The FRONTIERS newsletter will showcase the achievements and milestones reached by the project, spotlighting key milestones.

A content planner for the newsletter will be drafted by NOVA University Lisbon and agreed upon with the FRONTIERS partners. This planner will outline the main topics to be covered in each newsletter number and define a precise schedule for dissemination.

Newsletters will be designed and sent via Mailchimp every three months to all the subscribers. Promotion and dissemination of newsletters will happen through the project's website and social media accounts, ensuring broad reach and accessibility. In addition, an archive of all the projects' newsletters will be made available on the FRONTIERS' website.

Press Releases

Press releases will be sent to make specific announcements about the project, such as the opening of the science journalism residencies calls or the announcement of the selected fellows. These press releases will be sent to media organizations at the regional, national and international levels and each partner will be responsible for translating them into their regional languages. Media outlets specialized in science communication and science journalism will be prioritized. When relevant, press releases may be accompanied by video or audio material.

Press releases are scheduled to be prepared and sent on at least 10 separate occasions. Table II summarizes their content and tentative schedule.

Table II - Description of content and tentative schedule of planned press releases.

Press Releases	Description of Content	Tentative Schedule (in Project Months)
P1	Project Announcement	Between M1 and M3
P2	Announcement of 1 st open call	Between M6 and M9
P3	Announcement of selected fellows of 1 st call	Between M11 and M12
P4	Announcement of 2 nd open call	Between M12 and M15
P5	Announcement of selected fellows of 2 nd call	Between M17 and M18
P6	Announcement of 3 rd open call	Between M21 and M24
P7	Announcement of selected fellows of 3 rd call	Between M26 and M27
P8	Announcement of 4 th open call	Between M33 and M36

P9	Announcement of selected fellows of 4 th call	Between M38 and M39
P10	Promotion of Final Conference	Between M44 and M47

Events

The FRONTIERS consortium will organize and take part in several events aimed at communicating the project's goals, informing stakeholders about the project and disseminating its outputs.

Training

Training sessions will be organized and delivered by UPF, with the input of all project partners, throughout the project. These sessions will be an opportunity for the FRONTIERS fellows to learn more about frontier research and how institutions work firsthand. Moreover, the collaborative and interactive training among scientists and journalists will help researchers to better understand science journalism and the needs of the journalists. During the joint training activities, participants will also have the opportunity to establish networks and collaborations with other journalists and/or researchers around Europe.

Overall, FRONTIERS training activities will aim at i) strengthening collaboration between science journalists and researchers, ii) broadening the network of research institutions involved in the project, iii) communicating the projects' goals and methodologies and iv) informing about Frontier Science.

Training materials will be published in open access with support guidelines to help the training program implementation in other institutions. Training sessions and materials will be widely disseminated via the FRONTIERS website, social media and newsletter.

The training sessions will also provide opportunities to share the experience of FRONTIERS fellows and to promote the FRONTIERS Alumni network.

Conferences

At the end of the FRONTIERS project, a conference will be organized to present the results to key target audiences. The conference will be open to the general public, with a specific session dedicated to a wider audience, and it will take place in Lisbon, Portugal. NOVA University Lisbon will be in charge of the organisation of the conference.

Besides the final conference of the project, the FRONTIERS team will present the project at various scientific conferences, such as the Public Communication of Science and Technology (PCST) Conference and EuroScience Open Forum (ESOF), the Italian National Conference on Science Communication, the European Association of Communication Professionals in Higher Education (EUPRIO),

Associazione Italiana Comunicatori d'Università (AICUN), the South East Europe Media Forum (SEEMF) and others. These events are aimed mainly at science journalists, communication and press officers at research institutions and science communication enthusiasts. FRONTIERS' social media channels will be used to announce and highlight the partner's participation at such events.

Documentary

A documentary can be a powerful visual tool in the communication of the project. It can also be useful in developing or consolidating a narrative about FRONTIERS.

At the end of the project, NOVA University Lisbon will be responsible for the production of a 20 to 30-minute video documenting the experiences of science journalist fellows during their residencies. NOVA will also be in charge of producing and distributing clear guidelines for press officers at host institutions, with instructions on how to document and provide multimedia material to be included in the documentary,

The documentary will be made available on the project's website and on the project's YouTube channel, and will be widely disseminated on social media and on the FRONTIERS newsletter.

7. Monitoring of Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Activities

The impact of the FRONTIERS communication strategy will be assessed and closely monitored using website statistics, social media metrics, and others. Data gathered will be used to adjust the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities established in this deliverable. Data collection, storage and processing under the project's scope comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), thus ensuring that personal data is processed in a secure and transparent manner.

KPIs will be used as a guideline to grasp the success of the communication strategy. At M24, in the middle of the project, the FRONTIERS team will review and, if needed, adjust these KPIs, to conform with external changes that may affect the monitoring of the communication activities (e.g. disruptions in social media platforms, global health crisis, etc.).

Dissemination Activities

Activities	Description	KPIs
Presentations at international conferences	Presentations from the FRONTIERS team at national and international conferences.	4+ presentations
Dissemination of residency program call and information	The call for manifestation of interest by researchers and research Institutions and the application forms for science journalists will be disseminated via the FRONTIERS communication channels.	At least 10 applications in year 1 of the project, and yearly growth of +5 applications
Journalistic outputs	Dissemination of journalistic outputs generated during the residencies	30+ outputs, in different mediums and formats
	Dissemination of the outputs and experiences of science journalists during and after the completion of the residencies.	10+ one-week take-overs on social media channels
Journalistic experience	<p>Website (Profiles of fellows, short testimonials)</p> <p>Social Media (Presentations of Fellows, Takeover by science journalists, dissemination of short videos)</p> <p>Newsletter (Profiles of fellows)</p>	<p>30+ posts from host researchers and/or research institutions</p> <p>1 short video</p>

per residency

Training content and resources	Dissemination of training guidelines, tools and best practices to improve collaboration between science journalists and researchers.	6+ training resources
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Communication Activities

Activities	Description	KPIs
Website	<p>Setting up and maintaining the FRONTIERS website.</p> <p>Updating the website with content, materials, guidelines, and other information produced during the project.</p>	<p>Monthly unique visitors: 1k</p> <p>Number of yearly pageviews: 50k <i>(after the opening of the first calls)</i></p>
Social media	<p>Creating accounts on Twitter, LinkedIn and Instagram.</p> <p>Social media accounts will be regularly updated with content previously defined in the content planner.</p> <p>A YouTube account will be created after the start of the first residencies and will be used to publish short residency videos and the final documentary.</p>	<p>1k followers on average</p> <p>2 percent engagement rate on the posts</p>
Press releases	Press releases about the project will be sent to several media outlets all over Europe.	At least 40 press releases (in English and national languages)
Newsletter	Every three months, the FRONTIERS newsletter to inform its subscribers about the project's progress, announce open calls and distribute relevant outputs.	500 subscribers
Documentary	The documentary will be published on the website of the	1k views on Youtube

	project, using a YouTube embedded player. It will also be distributed to several media outlets.	
Final Conferences	At the end of FRONTIERS, the final conference will be organised in Lisbon to present the results to key target audiences.	40-60 attendees Audience reach: 3k people (participants, social media followers, media dissemination, general public).

Exploitation Activities

FRONTIERS expects to develop a sustainable program of science journalistic residencies and to motivate science funders, media companies, philanthropists, and research institutions to develop and fund their own science journalism programs.

Monitoring of these activities will be made mostly by ensuring that activities follow the Best Practices guidelines defined during the course of the project.

Activities	Description	KPIs
Legacy e-Handbook	All residency project results useful for the replication of the residency program will be collected and distributed in a Legacy e-Handbook.	1 handbook
Network establishment	During the project, FRONTIERS will leverage the partners' networks to create and expand links between science journalists and host researchers and institutions.	N.A.
Paths towards financial sustainability	The consortium will actively explore in the different EU countries all possible financial support for the maintenance of the project beyond its granted duration.	N.A.

8. Conclusion

The WP5 of FRONTIERS is dedicated to the dissemination and communication activities and exploitation of the results achieved throughout the project. Its overall communication strategy aims at ensuring a wide awareness of the project's activities and results, described in detail in this deliverable, D5.2 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan.

FRONTIERS' Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan outlines a wide range of strategies and activities that will help achieve the project's objectives. Its successful implementation will ensure a phased, yet broad reach and engagement with stakeholders, through the appropriate communication channels. Additionally, continuous evaluation and monitoring of all activities, as well as quick adjustment of the messages when deemed necessary, will be crucial to achieving the goals set out in this deliverable.

This document is the initial version of a series of expected updates to the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan of the project. WP5 will work in close collaboration with other WPs to establish a fruitful program supporting science journalism residencies in European research institutions and explore paths towards sustainable residencies through additional funding channels.

ANNEXES

Annex I - Overview of the three main phases the communication activities, channels and target audiences

Phases	Objectives	Actions	Channel	KPIs	Target Audiences
Phase 1	Attracting science journalists and scientific institutions to apply to FRONTIERS residencies	Setting up the Project's website	Website	-	All
		Dissemination of the open calls	Website, Social Media, Newsletter, Press Releases. ERC channels. EC Funding and Tenders Portal.	.	Science Journalists, Research Institutions (Press Offices), Scientists /PIs at Research Institutions
Phase 2	Sharing the experiences of journalists and institutions during the residencies	Publication/republication/promotion of the journalistic outputs	Website, social media, newsletter	30+	All
		Organization of the final conference	Conference	1	All
		Production of the Project's	Website and	1	All

		Documentary	Social Media		
		Takeover of social media accounts by journalists	Social media	-	All
Phase 3	Ensuring the results and good practices of FRONTIERS are shared with potential funders, who could replicate the experience in other contexts.	Presentations at international science journalism and science communication conferences	Events & Conferences	4+	Journalists, Scientific Community, Science Journalism Associations
		Sharing the training contents and resources	Website, Newsletter	6+	Science Journalists, Research Institutions (Press Offices), Scientists /PIs at Research Institutions
		Distribution of the Legacy e-Handbook	Website, Social Media	1	Science Journalists, Research Institutions (Press Offices), Scientists /PIs at Research Institutions, Media Organizations, Policymakers

Annex III - Overview of Communication and Dissemination Activities, Channels and Tentative Schedule

Action	Description	Channel	Tentative Schedule
Presentation of the project		Social Media	M6 (10/11/2023)
Presentation of the team		Social Media	M6 (13-17/11/2023)
Presentation of the Advisory Board		Social Media	M6 (20-24/11/2023)
Frontier Research Projects	Publication of page	Website	M6
	Highlight Frontier Research Projects	Social Media	M6
Expression of Interest Form for Researchers and Research Institutions	Publication of Form	Website	M6
	Call to Action: Fill the Form	Social Media	M6
Teaser: Open Call	Teaser: 1 st Call opens soon	Social Media	M6
Participation in conferences	Highlight FRONTIERS' participation in "Convegno Nazionale di Comunicazione della Scienza" (Trieste)	Social Media	M6 (29/11/2023)
FRONTIERS Newsletter	Call to action: subscribe to FRONTIERS Newsletter	Social Media	M6
1 st Call Open	Publish Application Form	Website	M6
	Release Call Documents	Website	M6
	Promote Call	Social Media	M6
		Newsletter	M6
		Press Release	M6
Database of host research institutions and researchers	Publish the Database	Website	M7
	Promote the Database	Social Media	M7

ERC Pilot Project	Publish Highlight on website and testimonials on homepage	Website	M7
	Quotes from ERC Pilot Project participants	Social Media	M7
Deadline 1st Call	Reminder Deadline for applications	Social Media	M9
1st Call Results	Announce selected fellows	Social Media, Press Releases	M11
	Page with fellows' profiles	Website	M11
	Fellows' profiles	Social Media	M11
	Get to know the host institutions	Social Media	M11
Experiences from 1st selected fellows	Takeover of Accounts	Social Media	M12-M17 (TBD)
	Promote Short Video with experiences in residencies*	Social Media	M12-M17 (TBD)
Training	Advertise training for fellows	Social Media	M12-M17(TBD)
2 nd Call Open	Reminder to fill the application form	Social Media	M12
	Promote Call	Social Media	M12
		Newsletter	M12
		Press Release	M12
Deadline 2 nd Call	Reminder Deadline for applications	Social Media	M15
2 nd Call Results	Announce selected fellows	Social Media, Press Releases	M15
	Page with fellows' profiles	Website	M15
	Fellows' profiles	Social Media	M15
	Get to know the host institutions	Social Media	M15
Experiences from 2 nd selected fellows	Takeover of Accounts	Social Media	M15-M21 (TBD)

	Promote Short Video with experiences in residencies*	Social Media	M15-M21 (TBD)
Training	Advertise training for fellows	Social Media	TBD
3 rd Call Open	Reminder to fill the application form	Social Media	M21
	Promote Call	Social Media	M21
		Newsletter	M21
		Press Release	M21
Deadline 3 rd Call	Reminder Deadline for applications	Social Media	M24
3 rd Call Results	Announce selected fellows	Social Media, Press Releases	M26
	Page with fellows' profiles	Website	M26
	Fellows' profiles	Social Media	M26
	Get to know the host institutions	Social Media	M26
Experiences from 3 rd selected fellows	Takeover of Accounts	Social Media	M26-M32 (TBD)
	Promote Short Video with experiences in residencies	Social Media	M26-M32 (TBD)
Training	Advertise training for fellows	Social Media	(TBD)
4 th Call Open	Reminder to fill the application form	Social Media	M33
	Promote Call	Social Media	M33
		Newsletter	M33
		Press Release	M33
Deadline 4 th Call	Reminder Deadline for applications	Social Media	M36
4 th Call Results	Announce selected fellows	Social Media, Press Releases	M38

	Page with fellows' profiles	Website	M38
	Fellows' profiles	Social Media	M38
	Get to know the host institutions	Social Media	M38
Experiences from 4 th selected fellows	Takeover of Accounts	Social Media	M38-M44 (TBD)
	Promote Short Video with experiences in residencies*	Social Media	M38-M44 (TBD)
Training	Advertise training for fellows	Social Media	TBD
Documentary	Publication of the documentary	Website	M44
	Promotion of the Documentary	Social Media	M44-M45
		Newsletter	M44-M45
Final Conference	Promotion of the Final Conference	Social Media	M40-M46
		Press Release	M40-M46
		Newsletter	M40-M46
	Conference Page / Website section	Website	M40-M46
	Organisation of the Conference (Lisbon)	Events	M46
Legacy Handbook	Publication of the Legacy Handbook	Website	M46
	Dissemination of the Handbook	Social Media	M46